

Effect of organic and inorganic nitrogen in acid sandy soil on upland rice yield

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In an experiment during the 1986 cropping season, poultry manure alone and in combination was compared with urea and calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) in upland sandy loam and acidic soils of Amakama, Nigeria. The experimental design was a randomized complete block (RCB) with four replications.

Soil samples for analysis were taken after land preparation but before fertilizer application. Physical and chemical properties of the experimental soil are presented in Table 1. N was applied at 60 kg/ha. The poultry manure contained 0.66% N.

Poultry manure was incorporated 2 wk before planting, with 30 kg P and 40 kg K/ha applied basally. Urea and CAN were applied in 2 equal splits at 3 and 8 wk after planting. In the combinations, poultry manure at 30 kg N/ha was applied 2 wk before planting, and inorganic fertilizer at 30 kg N/ha was applied 8 wk after planting. Average monthly rainfall during crop growth was 218.8 mm.

The test crop was newly released upland rice FARO 41 (IRAT170). In the yield parameters considered, rice with poultry manure performed slightly, but not significantly, better than

Table 1. Physical and chemical analysis of experimental soil prior to planting, Amakama, Nigeria, 1986.

pH	4.6
Sand (%)	70.4
Silt (%)	10.4
Clay (%)	19.2
Organic matter (%)	1.025
N (%)	0.12
Available P (Bray I) (ppm)	50
K (meq/100 g)	0.40
Ca (meq/100 g)	0.66
Mg (meq/100 g)	0.96
Mn (ppm)	0.24
Zn (ppm)	5.8
Fe (ppm)	60.0

inorganic fertilizers (Table 2). The lack of significant difference could be attributed to considerable nutrient leaching on a sandy soil subjected to high rainfall for more than 6 mo of the year. Many and more vigorous weeds grew in poultry manure-treated plots. CAN depressed yield, even in

combination with poultry manure.

The results indicate that poultry manure can be used to supplement inorganic fertilizers. Poultry manure is cheap, easier to handle than other organic manure, and more available with an increase in the number of poultry farmers. □

Table 2. Response of yield parameters to N sources.^a Amakama, Nigeria, 1986.

N source	Tillers (no./m ²)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Poultry manure	156	135	79	104	3.3
Urea	153	139	80	98	3.2
Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN)	134	118	81	94	2.8
Poultry manure + urea	138	117	79	101	3.2
Poultry manure + CAN	137	133	79	79	3.1
No N fertilizer	130	120	81	79	2.6
CV (%)	14	15	—		12.0
LSD	ns	ns			ns

^ans = not statistically significant.

Effect of floodwater depth on ammonia volatilization loss from urea in flooded soil

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Rate of ammonia volatilization in flooded rice soils can be estimated by monitoring floodwater parameters. But water depth may itself greatly influence the floodwater chemistry, and may influence rate of ammonia loss. We studied the effect of floodwater depth on ammonia volatilization, using a forced-draft chamber technique.

The soil was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrepts), pH 7.5, EC 0.15 dS/m, 0.32% organic C, 0.06% total N, and CEC 4.5 meq/100 g. Soil samples of 5 kg each were collected from the top 15 cm soil layer, air-dried, ground, and placed in 10-liter pots.

The soil was flooded, puddled, and allowed to preincubate with 1 cm standing water for 1 wk. It was then fertilized with 26 mg P and 50 mg K/kg, applied as single superphosphate and muriate of potash. Urea at 1.36 g N/pot (equivalent to 200 kg N/ha) was

broadcast and incorporated to 5–7 cm soil depth. The pots were reflooded to 25, 50, 100, and 125 mm depths. Evaporation losses were replenished daily.

Floodwater temperature ranged from 28 to 34 °C. Two pots of each treatment were covered with chambers continuously flushed with NH₃-free compressed air. NH₃ evolved from the incubated samples was collected at

1. Effect of floodwater depth on cumulative loss of ammonia from flooded sandy loam soil, Ludhiana, India.

Floodwater ammoniacal-N (g/m^3)

2. Effect of floodwater depth on ammoniacal-N concentration in the water. Ludhiana, India.

intervals using a manifold and estimated by absorbing in 2% boric acid-mixed indicator solution. Floodwater samples also were analyzed for ammoniacal- and urea-N.

Floodwater depth significantly affected rate of NH_3 volatilization in flooded Ludhiana soil (Fig. 1). At 4 d after application, 1.8% of added urea was volatilized in 25-mm-deep water, but only a trace was volatilized in deeper water. At 11 d, NH_3 volatilization was 7.5, 4.5, 1.8, and 0.5% of added urea in 25, 50, 100, and 125 mm-deep-water, respectively.

Ammoniacal-N concentration in the floodwater 4 d after urea application was greatest at 25-mm-deep water and least at 125 mm (Fig. 2). □

Efficiency of modified nitrogen fertilizers in rice on partially reclaimed saline soil

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We compared sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and prilled urea (PU) at 0, 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg

Table 1. Effect of source and rate of N on grain yield of rice. Dalipnagar, India, 1982-83 wet season.

N (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)			
	PU	USG	SCU	Mean
0	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.5
29	2.0	2.3	2.4	2.2
58	2.5	2.8	2.8	2.7
87	2.9	3.2	3.2	3.1
116	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.4
Mean	2.5	2.7	2.7	

LSD (0.05) 0.187

N/ha in rice on partially reclaimed saline soil at the Dalipnagar research farm during 1982-83 wet season.

Experimental soil was loamy with pH 8.7, EC 183 dS/m at 25 °C, 0.039% total N, 135-8-214 available NPK/ha.

Treatments were PU best split, USG deep placed (10-12 cm soil depth) 1 wk after transplanting Jaya variety, and

Composting with rice straw

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Rice straw is an important source of organic matter in rice-growing areas, but applying it directly into soil has a number of limitations. Composting appears to be an alternative.

Composting originated in upland cropping areas, where the basic raw materials are crop stovers other than rice straw and farmyard manure (primarily horse manure). We tested composting with rice straw and pig manure (pigs are the basic livestock in rice-growing areas in China).

The essential factors for composting were defined as optimal C:N ratio of around 40 in raw materials; chopped rice straw, mixed with grasses and leguminous leaves or tender tips, if available; pig manure or other farmyard manure; superphosphate at 3% of total raw material weight; appropriate moisture and aeration conditions.

The temperature at the center of the pile was raised to 70 °C across 34 d,

Table 2. Influence of source and N rate on N recovery.

N (kg/ha)	N recovery (%)			
	PU	USG	SCU	Mean
29	42.86	63.21	69.28	58.45
58	40.10	54.30	55.75	50.05
87	39.00	46.75	47.60	44.45
116	37.00	41.55	42.15	40.23
Mean	39.74	51.45	53.69	

SCU broadcast and incorporated at transplanting. P and K were applied uniformly at 26-25 kg/ha. ZnSO_4 was applied to the nursery bed at 25 kg/ha.

SCU and USG were significantly superior to PU at all N levels (Table 1), with a greater difference at lower N levels.

N recovery was highest with SCU (Table 2). Recovery of N decreased linearly with increase in N level. □

maintained for about 1 wk, then dropped gradually (see figure). Superphosphate showed some effect on keeping temperatures high, resulting in better compost maturity. Composting was completed in 45 to 60 d when N content was 0.3-0.4% and C:N ratio was 20.

The compost was used as basal manure for double-cropped rice. Table 1 gives the recovery of nutrients, Table 2 shows effect of rice straw compost on yield. Yields with rice straw compost were comparable to yield with conventional manure.

Temperature during composting. JAAS, Nanjing, Jiangsu, China.